

Strategies to Enhance Teaching and Learning of Physical Education in Junior secondary schools in Udi Local Government Area of Enugu State Nigeria.

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine Strategies To Enhance Teaching And Learning Of Physical Education In Junior Secondary Schools In Udi Local Government Area Of Enugu State Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was used in the study. The population for this study comprises of all 35 physical and health education teachers in all the (11) Public Secondary Schools in Ojebogene clan in Udi Local Government. Results of the study includes; it can be inferred that the availability of teaching tools like Table Tennis and swimming pool facilities, a sufficient soccer field and standard handball court, as well as first aid supplies, improves the teaching and learning of physical and health education for secondary school students. The study also discovered that teachers' use of discussion and demonstration, structured group learning, participatory learning, and question-and-answer techniques were well-liked as teaching strategies that improved the teaching and learning of physical and health education among secondary school students. Conclusion and recommendations include; The Enugu State government should make an effort to provide teaching resources for secondary schools in Udi Local Government that will further improve the teaching and learning of the subject. The secondary schools in the Udi Local Government should employ appropriate teaching strategies that might improve the delivery of physical education lessons and student learning.

Introduction

Secondary education's overarching objective is to prepare students for further education and meaningful living in society. To do this, the junior secondary curriculum's general goal is to advance students' understanding. The traditional bridge between the primary and tertiary stages of education is secondary education. It is the educational level intended to mold young minds going through many emotional, physiological, and psychological transformations at the time. The secondary school curriculum includes a physical education (PE) component. A curriculum for physical education has been developed, put into place, and evaluated to encourage students to lead healthy lives, Learn to choose nutritious foods, and spend less time watching television and playing video games.(Sallis and Mckenzie ,2001). All children should be able to participate in structured physical exercise in school settings when it comes to physical education. It is also the responsibility of the school to ensure that they have a ton of fun and delight while avoiding making them feel ashamed of or teased by others for their lack of technical proficiency. The school has a responsibility to keep students engaged (and thus healthy). As straightforward it may seem, it is important to keep in mind that people do not decide to lead an active life or to play a specific sport at any one time or under the influence of a single element. It is obtained through a process, which is physical education. Providing physical education is undoubtedly one of the most challenging processes since it calls for a blend of pedagogical expertise and biological knowledge. However, this wasn't always so evident. In the past, the physical education program was eliminated from the curriculum because many schools cut recess and physical education time to provide more time for sedentary classroom instruction as they attempt to improve the academic performance of their pupils (Stewart et al, 2009). Without a doubt, the Physical and Health Education course is of the utmost importance to the entire student body, notwithstanding their disparities in age, status, and educational background. As a result, the teacher is the foundation for both learning and teaching and the most crucial element in the educational process. The teacher is regarded as the primary and first tool in education. In order to prepare future generations of learners and to

address issues that limit their capacity to carry out tasks reflected in student progress and level-leveraging, schools rely on teachers. Recess and physical education in schools are essential for children's development, according to research, and not merely as a means of preventing obesity and other weight-related problems. Research have indicated that initiatives aimed at enhancing the quality of physical education can increase the proportion of the class period devoted to moderate to vigorous physical activity MVPA to more than 50%. Students can acquire the necessary information, abilities, habits, and confidence to be physically active for life by creating and executing high-quality physical education (PE) programs. Academic performance of secondary school pupils has declined despite physical education programs being taught and implemented in schools. Physical education programs in some schools still use the same teaching methods, where students share a single ball to play a particular sport in a large group. The disadvantage is that not every child has the chance to play. The value of physical education classes has increased for pupils as a result of the implementation of new curricula, proper equipment, teaching methods, etc. In order to comply with the six National Association of Sport and Physical Education (NASPE) standard guidelines, researchers and educators are working to improve their curricula and training methods, demonstrates an understanding of movement concepts, principles, strategies, and tactics as they relate to learning and performing physical activities, engages in regular physical activity, reaches and maintains a level of physical fitness that is health-improving, and demonstrates competency in motor skills and movement patterns necessary to perform a variety of physical activities, Values physical exercise for health, enjoyment, challenge, self-expression, and/or social connection, and demonstrates appropriate personal and social behaviour that respects self and others in physical activity situations.

Examining the necessary tactics to be used to improve the teaching and learning of physical and education in junior secondary schools is now critically important given that the reasons behind students' poor performance in physical education are now known, and their performance must be improved.

Purpose of the Study

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This study's primary goal is to identify several strategies to enhance the teaching and learning of physical education in junior secondary schools in Udi Local Government Area of Enugu State

Specifically, the research would determine whether:

1. Having instructional materials available improves physical education teaching and learning.
2. A good teaching strategy improves physical and health education instruction and student learning.
3. Hiring qualified instructors improves the delivery of physical and health education instruction.
4. A supportive setting improves the delivery of physical and health education instruction.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. Would Having instructional materials improve physical education teaching and learning in Udi LGA?
2. Would a good teaching strategy improve the delivery of physical and health education in Udi LGA?
3. Would the teaching and learning of physical and health education in Udi LGA be improved by the hiring of trained teachers?
4. Would a supportive setting improve the delivery of physical and health education in the Udi LGA?

METHODS

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A descriptive survey design was used in the study. The area of the Study is UDI Local Government of Enugu State. Udi Local Government is made up of clans like, Umuneke, Ezedike, Ojebogene, Ugwunye, Ngwo, Oshie. The population for this study comprises of all 35 physical and health education teachers in all the (11) Public Secondary Schools in Ojebogene clan in Udi Local Government. There was no sample as the population was used. Data for the study were gathered using a questionnaire that was prepared for researchers. Mean was used for data analysis;

Research question 1: Would having instructional materials improve physical education teaching and learning in Udi LGA?

Table 1: Respondents mean responses on provision of instructional materials

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	Remark
1	Availability of Table Tennis Facility can enhance student's Learning	10	9	7	9	2.5	Accepted
2	Students can improve if adequate Soccer pitch is provided for them	10	10	5	10	2.6	Accepted
3	Swimming Pool is an important Facility for the enhancement of Student's learning	15	10	4	6	2.9	Accepted
4	Availability of standard Handball court makes teaching more practical	8	17	8	2	2.8	Accepted
5	Availability of first aid materials Encourages students participation In sports	7	13	9	6	2.6	Accepted

According to table 4.1 above, all of the elements were accepted with the mean scores of 2.5 and higher. This suggests that the availability of teaching resources, such as Table Tennis and swimming pool facilities, suitable soccer fields and standard handball courts, as well as first aid supplies, increases the teaching and learning of physical and health education for secondary school students.

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Research Question 2: Would a good teaching strategy improve the delivery of physical and health education in Udi LGA?

Table 4.2 Respondents mean responses on proper teaching method

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	Remark
6	Teachers use demonstration to improve students understanding	10	10	5	10	2.6	Accepted
7	Organised group learning helps teachers observe student interactive ability	12	12	6	5	2.8	Accepted
8	Participatory learning activities helps to facilitate critical thinking	11	15	4	5	2.9	Accepted
9	Teachers use discussion to get the students involved in class activities	8	14	5	8	2.6	Accepted
10	Question and answer method helps to test the knowledge of the students	15	5	6	9	2.7	Accepted

The result in table 4.2, shows that teacher’s use of demonstration and discussions, organized group learning, participatory learning and question and answer methods were accepted as teaching methods that enhances the teaching and learning of physical and health education as shown in items 6-10 with mean scores of 2.5 and above.

Research Question 3: Would the teaching and learning of physical and health education in Udi LGA be improved by the hiring of trained teachers?

Table 4.3: Respondents mean responses on quality teachers.

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	Remark
11	Teachers with formal training gives the best to their students	7	18	3	7	2.7	Accepted
12	Teaching for a reasonable number of years helps to better manage their students	16	6	8	5	2.9	Accepted
13	Students learn and understands more when their teachers are dedicated	12	11	6	6	2.8	Accepted
14	Monitoring of students' learning helps the teacher to assess the students and carry everybody along	8	17	6	4	2.8	Accepted
15	Caring and fair teachers sees to the need of their students	19	10	4	2	3.3	Accepted

Table 4.3 shows that all of the items had mean rating scores of 2.5 or higher, indicating that the teachers' formal training, years of experience, dedication, and monitoring of students' progress, as well as their fair and caring treatment of students, are all teaching qualities that improve the teaching and learning of physical and health education among secondary school students.

Research Question 4: Would a supportive setting improve the delivery of physical and health education in the Udi LGA?

Table 4.4: Respondents mean responses on Conducive Environment

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	Remark
16	A Physically attractive environment can have a positive impact on quality of student interactions	15	8	5	7	2.8	Accepted
17	Using relevant materials helps teachers to manage their time for the class.	12	12	3	8	2.8	Accepted
18	Teacher's good classroom control improves the behaviour and achievements of the students	13	11	5	6	2.8	Accepted
19	Effective teachers establishes positive relationship with their students	12	15	3	5	2.9	Accepted
20	A disordered class arrangement affects learning negatively	15	9	6	5	2.9	Accepted

The outcome from table 4.4 shows that a physically appealing environment, the use of pertinent materials by the teacher, good classroom management, the teacher's positive relationship with their students, and an orderly classroom arrangement are conducive environments that enhance the teaching and learning of physical and health education. The results in Table 4.4 indicate that all of the items had mean scores of 2.5 or higher and were therefore acceptable.

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings demonstrated that providing secondary school pupils with access to instructional resources such table tennis courts, a sufficient soccer field, and a normal handball court improves the teaching and learning of physical and health education.

The study also discovered that teachers' use of discussion and demonstration, structured group learning, and the question-and-answer approach were

acknowledged as effective teaching strategies for secondary school students' physical and health education instruction. The study also found that formal teacher training, years of classroom experience, commitment to tasks, and oversight of student learning are all aspects of teaching that improved the delivery and comprehension of physical and health education to secondary school students. Additionally, a physically appealing atmosphere, a teacher who maintains strong classroom discipline, a teacher who has a positive relationship with their pupils, and a classroom that is organized well all contribute to the teaching and learning of physical and health education. This means that if strategies like the provision of instructional materials, teaching methodology, quality of teachers, and conducive environment are properly applied, they can enhance the teaching and learning of Physical and Health Education in secondary schools and improve students' academic achievements. This is aligned with Adunola (2011), said that the majority of students' poor academic achievement is mainly related to teachers' use of inadequate teaching strategies to impart knowledge to students.

Conclusion

Five chosen secondary schools in Enugu State's Udi Local Government Area served as the subject of this study. The goal of the research was to identify methods for improving the delivery of physical education and health education in Udi Local Government Area of Enugu State. The results of this study's data analysis demonstrated that good teaching practices and the supply of instructional resources were effective strategies for improving physical and health education teaching and learning.

The research' findings show that in Udi Local Government Area of Enugu State, teaching and learning of physical and health education are made easier by good teachers and the availability of a supportive learning environment.

Recommendations

From the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Enugu State government should make an effort to provide teaching resources for secondary schools in Udi Local Government that will further improve the teaching and learning of the subject.
2. The secondary schools in the Udi Local Government should employ appropriate teaching strategies that might improve the delivery of physical education lessons and student learning.
3. The government should make an effort to hire skilled educators and give them the training they need to handle the teaching and learning of the subject.
4. A good and conducive learning environment with adequate facilities and equipment should be provided to secondary schools in Udi Local government Area of Enugu State.

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